

Garadaghli Genocide

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In the history of the World, in 1918, the Hays (Armenians), who did not have a "state", with the full support of Tsarist Russia, regional and international forces, created the Republic of Armenia in the historical lands of Azerbaijan. Great powers They skillfully used the "Armenian card" against the Ottoman Empire and the Republic of Turkey. All historical facts, sources, documents, historical religious and spiritual monuments prove that Karabakh was the territory of Azerbaijan.

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Introduction

The settlement of Armenians in the South Caucasus, including Karabakh, began in the early 19th century in accordance with Russia's strategic plan. Although a plan to resettle Armenians in the South Caucasus was prepared during the reign of Peter I, it was not possible to fully implement it at that time. Favorable conditions for the implementation of this plan appeared in the early nineteenth century.

Keywords: Karabakh, Azerbaijan, occupation, Genocide, conflict, Garadaghli

The Dashnaksutyun party, founded in the late 19th century, spread the idea of "Armenianism" aimed primarily at the destruction of the Turkic and Muslim peoples, in order to create a mythical state with baseless claims such as the creation of a "Greater Armenia from sea to sea" or "Greater Armenia from the Black Sea to the Caspian Sea." was. In the realization of this idea, the massacres, terrorist acts, genocides, robberies, etc. committed by Armenians all over the world. carried out.¹

In January 1992, Armenian terrorist groups killed 80 civilians in Karkijahan settlement, 77 people in Garadagli village of Khojavend region in February 1992, and 613 civilians in Khojaly city on February 26, 1992, and seriously injured 650 people.

In order to inform the world community about the Garadaghli tragedy, the documentaries "Genocide: Garadagli", "Genocide Garadagli: continues ..." and "Garadaghli, struggle" were made, and the book "Garadaghli genocide in the language of witnesses" was published. Of course, with the full support of the realities of Azerbaijan, international and regional forces, the Ottoman Empire, the Caucasus, Central Asia and the historical lands of Azerbaijan have historically witnessed the terror, ethnic cleansing, genocides, robberies, crimes, etc. committed by Armenians. Works, books and articles should be written and delivered to the international community in foreign languages. The decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Heydar Aliyev on March 26, 1998 on the "Genocide of Azerbaijanis" played a role in informing international organizations and the world community about the criminal actions of Armenians.

¹ Subhan Talibli - What are the main and factual land claims of Armenians over Karabakh? COMMENT-

<https://sia.az/en/news/social/771630.html>

Historical and natural-geographical position of Garadaghli

Garadagli village is a village located in Garadagli village of Khojavend district of the Republic of Azerbaijan . It is located 13 km west of the center of Khojavend region, on the side of Khojavend-Khankendi highway, in the foothills. The population was mainly engaged in animal husbandry, grain growing, cocooning, viticulture and melon growing. The village has clans and descendants named Garadagli, Mirzali, Mirzakhanli, Mashammadli, Usuflu, Mammazali, Varandali, Ali, Tagili, Mammadsafili, Gamjilli, Gulparilar, Abulhasanli. Shushu, Ituchan rock, Nagy forest, Heydar garden, Snow stone, Namaz dead road, Shirin forest, Sebi forest, Cotton valley, Dark valley, Manas valley, Manas plain, Musa valley, Pishikli valley, Dahna valley, Varandeli valley, Beylik garden , Baba spring, Mehmet spring, Beylik spring, Snow stone spring, Çanak spring, Hazelnut spring, Gorgali spring, Flower spring, Varandeli spring, etc. geographical names were recorded.

The toponym Garadagh is a combination of the words black and mountain. The word black means "great" and "color" in the ancient Turkic language. So, the word Garadagh means "big, high mountain", "mountain with black color of rocks". The word "mountain" is found in the ancient Turkic written monuments of the VI-VIII centuries in the dictionary of Mahmud of Kashgar (XI century), ²in the epics "Kitabi-Dada Gorgud".

After the establishment of the Soviet government in Azerbaijan, ie in 1928, a primary school of I-IV grades was established in Garadagli village, in 1956 the school was expanded to an 8-year basic school, and in 1974 to a full secondary school. On the eve of the occupation (1991-1992 academic year), the number of students studying at the school was more than 350. In 1951, Varandali village, inhabited by Azerbaijanis, was abolished and merged with Garadagli village without any need. This was the next stage of the Armenian intrigue (purposeful policy) in Karabakh. Thus, the names of the villages inhabited by Azerbaijanis were purposefully changed, merged with other villages or completely abolished and the resettlement of the population was organized. The aim was to change the demographic situation in the Autonomous Region in favor of the Armenians, to create a basis for separatist and terrorist acts. The Garadagli village soviet (executive office), which functioned until that period, was also abolished and merged with the Armenian village soviet Gagarza. At the same time, the Garadagli village collective farm was abolished and merged with the farms of the villages inhabited by Armenians in the collective farm named after Michurin. In 1971, Garadagli village was separated from Armenian villages and established a collective farm named after

"Nariman Narimanov", and on October 2, 1980, the activity of Garadagli village council was restored.³

The settlement was established as a result of the settlement of the Garadagli tribe of Qizilbash, who played a major role in the struggle for power of the Safavid state . The tribe got its name from the Garadagh district of South Azerbaijan . After the Safavids came to power, the people of Garadagh spread to different areas. The villages named Garadagli also reflect the ethnic name of the families belonging to this tribe. Until the 30s of the XX century, there was a village called Garadagli near Gulebird village of Lachin region. The name of this village is mentioned in a bayat of Sari Ashig ^{4,5}

Organization of the attack on Garadaghli

Arabo ⁶and Aramo units and Monte Melkonian's group took part in the attack on Garadaghli. The 366th

³ Pagayeva Q., Aslanov Sh . Garadaghli Genocide: In the language of martyrs. (Dedicated to the memory of the victims of the genocide committed by the Armenian Armed Forces in Garadagli village of Khojavend region of Azerbaijan). Baku, "Science and education", 2013, p. 31-33

⁴ Sari Ashig (16th century, Lachin region - 17th century, Gulabrid) is a bayati master. The exact date of birth and death of Sari Ashug, one of the Azerbaijani ashugs of the 17th century, is unknown. Sari Ashig was born and lived in the village of Garadagli, which existed in the XVII-XIX centuries on the right bank of the Hakari River near the village of Gulabrid, Lachin region, and is now buried in the territory of the present Gulebird village near Garadagli village. Ashig's grave is located in Gulebird village of Zangazur district, now Lachin region, near Hakari river. An imaginary image of him is engraved on the headstone of the tomb.

⁵Encyclopedic dictionary of toponyms of Azerbaijan. In II volume, II volume, Baku: "East-West", 2007, p. 24.

⁶ Arabo volunteer group (Armenian- Արաբո կամավորական ջոկատ , Arabo kamavorakan jokat in Latin script) or Arabo battalion - a nationalist paramilitarist group consisting mainly of Armenian Armenians and Armenians from abroad in the Karabakh war . The group was originally called Garegin Njde . However, the emergence of a group called "Garegin Njde" among other Armenian groups led to the change of the group's name to "Arabo". "Arabo" was the pseudonym of Stepanos

² "Kitab-i Dadem Gorgud ala lisan-i taife-i Oguzan" (Book of Dadem Gorgud in the language of Oghuz tribes) - Oghuz Turkic epic. The oldest written monument of Azerbaijani folk literature (VI-VII centuries).

Motorized Rifle Regiment was also used during the attack on the village.⁷

The command staff of the 366th Motorized Rifle Regiment said it could not secure the regiment's release due to public opposition.⁸ For this purpose, the forces of the landing division located in Ganja had to be involved. However, before the arrival of these forces, 103 members of the regiment, mainly Armenians, who took part in the massacre, refused to obey the order and remained in Karabakh. As a result of the criminal deal of the regiment's command and the irresponsibility of other persons responsible for the withdrawal of the regiment, part of the military equipment, including armored vehicles, was handed over to the Armenians.⁹

These forces took part in the Garadaghli and Khojaly genocides.¹⁰ Witnesses of the Garadaghli genocide

confirm the participation of the 366th motorized infantry regiment in the act of genocide.¹¹

Occupation of Garadaghli

The operation to evacuate civilians from Garadaghli, which began in the summer of 1991, was almost completed by the end of the year. On the eve of the occupation, Garadaghli was defended by 125 people. Only 14 of them were fighters of the National Army who came to help from Agdam, and 70 were fighters of the Garadaghli self-defense group. In addition, 17 men over the age of 60 and 13 school-age children were ready to fight. Eleven women over the age of 50 volunteered to help their husbands, sons and brothers in the village. Heroic Azerbaijani women Ziver, Sitara, Tavar, Gerekmez, Mina, Minara, Saadat, Mirvari, Minaya, Guler and Haqiqat have helped 125 people since December.

As a result of the terrorist attack on September 8, 1991, a passenger bus coming from Aghdam to Garadaghli was ambushed by Armenian militants ambushing 5 km of the Khojavend-Khankendi road. When the bus was hit by bullets, 8 out of about 40 passengers, including 2 young men and 6 women, were killed.

On January 15, 1992, the people of Garadaghli addressed the people of Azerbaijan for the last time, and this appeal was announced on the radio for several days. The text of the appeal was as follows: "The cruel atrocities of history cannot in the slightest shake the sons of the fighters who stand guard over the land of Karabakh and bravely try to overcome the most difficult trials of the time. For four years, Garadaghli, a piece of Karabakh's pearl, has been targeted by the enemy, but it is protected by its fearless sons. The residents of this forgotten village, which has not been engraved in our memory for years, are living the most difficult days of their lives. Dwellings, various administrative buildings are set on fire, innocent people are killed, property is looted. In short, he is constantly attacked by Armenian bandits. Enemies want to seize this beautiful, important position. After all, Garadaghli cut off the road between Khojavend and Khankendi, once prevented their movement on this road! The situation in Garadaghli became even more tense after the occupation of Khojavend by bandits. My native people! If there is a sign of honor and zeal in your blood, do not stop the struggle for the liberation of Karabakh! Otherwise,

Mixitaryan, who rebelled against the Ottomans in the 19th century .

⁷ 366th Motorized Rifle Regiment - a military unit of the former Soviet army based in Khankendi. Russia's 366th motorized infantry regiment, which wrote its name in black letters in the history of Azerbaijan, took part in both the Khojaly and Garadaghli tragedies (February 17, 1992). Thanks to this regiment, the Armenians achieved great success in the first years of the First Karabakh War.

Unfortunately, so far the commanders of the regiment have not been punished for their actions.

⁸ Салаев, Г. 40 days Khojaly: "heroes" 366th regiment is dedicated. Youth of Azerbaijan.- 1992.- April 4.- c.- 2

⁹ Литовкин, В. The paratroopers will cover the 366th regiment from Stepanakert. Izvestia.- 1992.- March 3.- c.1 ; see: Valiyev, X. The participation of servicemen and other persons of the 366th Regiment in the Khojaly genocide has been fully proved. New Azerbaijan.- 2011.- February 26.- p.11 ; Aliyoglu, S. Khojaly: [366 days have passed since the massacre committed by the "366th" division]. 525th Gazette.- 1993.- 26 February.- p. 4 .; Mammadov, E. Khojaly was under siege for four months: an operational plan was prepared at the headquarters of the 366th Motorized Rifle Regiment. Two coasts.- 2008.- 26 February.- p .5.

¹⁰ Today, Azerbaijan commemorates the 26th anniversary of the Garadaghli massacre committed by Armenian armed forces- <http://defence.az/en/news/124474/26-years-pass-since-garadaghly-massacre>

¹¹Garadaghly Massacre through the eyes of witness- <https://en.azvision.az/news/81073/garadaghly-massacre-through-the-eyes-of-witness.html>

Garadaghli can become a nest of bandits with your own hands."¹²

Early in the morning of February 15, Armenian military units attacked the village of Garadaghli from all sides. Fighters from neighboring Armenian villages, mercenaries, Russian officers and soldiers of the 366th Russian Regiment took part in the attack.

One of the tragic histories of the Azerbaijani people, the Garadaghli massacre or Garadaghli tragedy - Armenian military units attacked the Garadaghli village of Khojavend on February 14, 1992 with the help of military forces and equipment of the 366th motorized infantry regiment of the former USSR armed forces in Khankendi. Despite the heroic defense of the villagers, on February 17, Garadaghli village was occupied by Armenians in unequal battles.

Victims of genocide

On February 17, 1992, Garadaghli village was occupied by aggressive Armenian armed forces, and 118 people in the village were taken prisoner. Thirty-three of the captives, most of them young men, were brutally shot near the village, burying the dead and wounded in a farm well. Of the captives, 66 were killed and 52 were released with great difficulty. The vast majority of those who escaped from captivity died in a short time as a result of severe torture in captivity and injections of unknown composition.¹³

4 people from each of 2 families, 2 and 3 people from 6 families were killed in the village, 43 families lost their heads, both parents from 1 family were killed. One in 10 Garadaghli villagers was killed. Of those killed, 21 were elderly, 10 were women and 8 were schoolchildren. 146 children were orphaned.¹⁴ 91 people were killed in Garadaghli village during the genocide committed by Armenian terrorist gangs. As a result of the occupation, 200 houses, 1 house of culture, a 320-seat secondary school, a 25-bed hospital and other facilities, historical, religious, cultural monuments and a cemetery belonging to Azerbaijanis were destroyed in the village. About 800 residents of the village were displaced.¹⁵

Those killed while in Armenian captivity

After the occupation of the village, some of the captives were killed around the village, and some were

tortured to death in Khankendi¹⁶prison: Imran Ahmad oglu Huseynov, Boyukkishi Lala oglu Shirinov, Kamil Sardar oglu Tagiyev, Fazil Javad oglu Valiyev, Alastan Nariman oglu Guliyev, Shura Avdihuseyn oglu Huseynov, Shura Ibad oglu Nazarov, Kamal Baylar oglu Guliyev.

Those who died shortly after their release from captivity

held captive in Khankendi and Askeran for more than 2 months . They died shortly after their release from captivity as a result of severe torture and suffering inflicted on them by Armenians, which was inhumane to them and violated the principles of all international law against the captives. Their list is as follows: 1. Familat Garay oglu Shirinov 2. Zulumkhan Mirish oglu Huseynov 3. Yusif Nariman oglu Guliyev 4. Minaya Samad gizi Amirkhanova 5. Sitara Samad gizi Huseynova 6. Mahammad Huseyn oglu Hasanov (son was martyred) 7. Gulu Eyyub oglu Khalilov (brother was killed) 8. Shamil Ali oglu Mammadov 9. Sardar Gachay oglu Tagiyev (son and brother were killed) 10. Avaz Gachay oglu Tagiyev (brother was killed) 11. Mirvari Tahmaz gizi Huseynova 12. Gullar Dostu gizi Tagiyeva 13. Mina Mirkhudar gizi Sadigov 14. Ilgar Gasim oglu Aliyev- (father was martyred) 15. Tevon Habil oglu Tagiyev (son was martyred) 16. Atlikhan Farman oglu Huseynov 17. Firudun Humbat oglu Huseynov.

Memories of witnesses during the Garadaghli genocide

Ilgar Huseynov is one of the villagers who witnessed the tragedy in Garadaghli . He and his family were taken hostage by Armenians in February 1992. Ilgar Huseynov was in Armenian captivity for two months. From the words of Ilgar Huseynov: " There is no family in the Garadaghli community that does not get its share from the Armenian savagery. Our village was occupied in February 1992. But back in September 1991, the Armenians seized control of the Garadaghli community. On September 8, Armenians fired on the Agdam-Garadaghli bus. Eight people were killed on the spot and more than 10 innocent people were seriously

¹⁶Karabakh khanate in the 18th century under the name Khankendi (Khan's village). Central Executive Committee of the Azerbaijan SSR after the establishment of the Soviet government On July 7, 1923, by the decree "On the establishment of the Nagorno-Karabakh Autonomous Reg

ion", Khankendi was declared the center of the region. In September 1923, the city was renamed "Stepanakert" after S. Shaumyan. In 1991, by the decision of the Supreme Soviet of the Azerbaijan SSR, the former and historical name of the city "Khankendi" was restored.

¹² Zulfugarli MP Garadaghli tragedy: Armenian terror in Nagorno-Karabakh: February 17, 1992. Baku: 2010 , Law, p.10

¹³

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qarada%C4%9Fli%C4%B1_q%C9%99tiam%C4%B1

¹⁴ <http://www.xocavend-ih.gov.az/news/1056.html>

¹⁵

https://azertag.az/xeber/Qaradagli_faciesi_qurbanlarinin_xatiresi_anilib-1247282

injured. On February 15, 1992, the Armenians fired on Garadaghli from all sides. Most of the houses were on fire. The shooting lasted for two days. Of the remaining 118 people in the village, 25 died. Four people were seriously injured. We took the wounded at night and set off. There were 10 women and two children among us. Armenians were persecuting us. We could not resist them because our boss ran out.

Armenians captured everyone. They separated men from women and children and put us in separate cars. We were brought to the Armenian cemetery. They said that 9 people should volunteer. No one moved. Enraged, the Armenian bandits opened fire on the car with a machine gun. 10-15 people died on the spot. About 20 people were seriously injured. Seeing the seriousness of the situation, one of the villagers wanted to flee. His actions angered the Armenians even more. They fired at us again. The death toll rose to 32. Then they took us to Khankendi. We were detained in Khankendi prison for two months. The prison had no windows. It snowed every day. Frost worked on human bones. All the hostages were kept in knee-deep water. Once every three days, we were given hand-sized black bread.

Armenians we were beaten and tortured at least five or six times a day. Several died in prison because they could not stand the torture. Eight people had their ribs broken and their legs broken. Two people hit the wall and blew up their brains. They tortured not only men but also women and children. Two months later, with the help of the Red Cross, we were released. Several of my hostages died after their release. Although 19 years have passed since then, the pain of torture by Armenians is still with me.¹⁷

Mahammadali Bayramov, a resident of Garadaghi village, said that Armenians have been carrying out armed attacks since 1990: "Armenians killed three people who came to the village to sell furniture. Then one person was injured on a cattle farm near the village. In 1991, they started firing on both the village and the cattle farm. When we went to the farm, we saw that 6 people, including women, were burned. The cattle of the village were taken away as soon as they left. In 1992, the situation worsened. The villagers told me to go and get help. First, I came to the headquarters in Agdam. Malibeyli village was already occupied. Helicopters were needed to evacuate women, children and the elderly in Garadaghli. We went to Ganja to ask for a helicopter. From there we returned empty-handed. Together with self-defense groups and police, we did not want to cross from Agdam to Khojavend. On the way from Gulabli village to Garadaghli through the forest, we met our compatriot Vidadi Huseynov. He said that the village was occupied. Only he managed to escape. The people were taken to Khankendi ... Armenians committed terrible crimes against the residents of our village. Four members of our family - my father, brother, sister - were killed, and one brother went missing ... "

Village resident Malahat Tagiyeva: "Garadaghli is our wounded and painful place. Our people have suffered a lot. Almost every family in the village has faced a tragedy. I lost my father, brother, nephew, uncle, brother-in-law, uncles, cousins in Garadaghli. They were all my relatives. I left the village before the tragedy. I was 22 then. I will never forget. After the tragedy, we asked our relatives and missing people from our captives and hostages. What those people said terrified us. People were tortured, beaten, starved, had their teeth and nails pulled out ... It is impossible to forget this tragedy. I want Garadaghi to be named a heroic village. "

Oruj Aliyev, a witness to the tragedy, said that despite the passing of years, he was still horrified when he remembered those days: "Armenians attacked the village on February 14. We stubbornly resisted the enemy and fought day and night. On the 17th of the month, we ran out of bullets. The villagers were taken away in two KamAZ trucks. Some of us were brought on foot to the place called "Pir" on the outskirts of the village. Shahmurad was killed on the way. Here we got on a KamAZ, Eldar was knocked to the ground, beaten to death with a stick. When passing the Beylik garden, they stopped a KamAZ on the edge of the Tut garden. They said let 10 people fall. Telman threw the grenade he had taken with him at the Armenians. I do not know how many people died from the enemy. They started firing at us. Most of the people in the car were killed. I was injured. Then we set off. On the way, they dropped Elmdar. We did not know about him. I and several villagers were separated from other villagers on the Malibeyli bridge and taken to Khankendi. We were beaten until the morning. When I went out in the morning, I saw that our people fell to the ground in front of the prison, and Armenians were walking here and there. They put us in a KamAZ and brought us to Askeran. Our hard days began in Asgaran. We were tortured, beaten and starved. One day, the Armenian supervisor told Ilgar that if you did not remove the hair from one side of your face with your hands until the morning, I would shoot you. Until the morning, one of us pulled out the hairs on Ilgar's face, the other blew ... Then Ilgar was taken away from us. Two Garadaghli residents and 28 Khojaly residents were together. We were taken away and beaten every day. Three days after the occupation of Khojaly, I was beaten again. When I returned, they put me in the cell where the Khojaly people were detained, not in the cell where I stayed. The interior was full of Khojaly residents. Armenians often came, opened the door and killed the occupants with knives and pistols. By morning, four of the survivors had been killed. Our people attacked Askeran from Aghdam. The Armenians left Askeran, took us to the village of Noragah and put us in the basement of the warehouse. The Armenians pulled out the gold teeth of me and other hostages. We stayed there for 43 days. They kept him in the water, beat him and tortured him. Several residents of Khojaly died of starvation, cold and beatings ... Today I am alive and well, but I carry with me what I suffered in

¹⁷ 2nd Khojaly genocide - 19th anniversary of Garadaghli tragedy completed-- <http://www.yalquzaq.com/?p=18069>

captivity, those terrible days, suffering as a heavy burden."¹⁸

From Huseynova Hagigat's words: "Armenian militants surrounded us. What did our eyes not see? - Our villager Eldar was killed from a tree in front of our eyes. - From the tree, knocking. He was killed in the village on the side of the road, on the asphalt, in a place called "Pir". They fell down, beat him to death with a stick. Then they killed my daughter-in-law's father. I did not know what they hit, but the man's head was torn in two. Then they put it under the car and made it unrecognizable. Our villager named Zahid was killed near the village of Society (Ningi). When his brother wanted to shout, I put my hand over his mouth so that his voice could not be heard. He had bitten my hand until it bled. His name was Vagif ... May God have mercy on your dead, he could not stand those sufferings and died."¹⁹

From the words of Nofal Aliyev: "We were captives in Khankendi prison. We had a young villager - in the name of the motherland, he was taken to kill in front of me. I asked the Armenian who was supervising us in prison, where did they take that child? He said that they took him to our cemetery, to behead him on the grave ... He was killed with such brutality ... We were kept in cells five, five, six. Each of the five captives was given a piece of bread a day and a small glass of water. We just wet our lips with that small glass of water so that we wouldn't die ... We were tortured all day. If Armenians had gold teeth, they were forcibly taken out of the captives' mouths. Anyone who tried to resist was beaten to death. I was also forced to have my teeth extracted."²⁰

Sabira Mahmudova, one of the female officers of the Azerbaijani National Army, is also one of the witnesses to the genocide. He said: "A helicopter carrying food to Garadagli, which has been under siege for a long time, was shot down by Armenians on January 12, 1992, and the villagers were left to their fate ... In early February, the Armenian Armed Forces attacked Gardagli again with the help of the 366th Motorized Rifle Regiment. The population continued to resist. It was announced on January 15 that they would fight to the last drop of blood ... Since the summer of 1991,

children, the elderly and women have been evacuated from the village by helicopters. There were about 11 women left in the village to look after their sons, husbands and prepare food for the soldiers ... On February 14, the Armenians attacked the village again ... I can still hear gunshots and screams of innocent people ..."²¹

Confessions of Armenians about the genocide committed in Garadagli

The book "My Brother's Way" by Markar Melkonian, the brother of the international terrorist Monte Melkonian, one of the leading figures of the "Asala" terrorist organization, who committed terrorist acts against Turkish politicians and Turks in general in France, the United States, Lebanon and a number of other European countries, reads²²: He calmly put the B-7 on his shoulder, picked up the target, and pressed the trigger. With the roar of the first shell, he entered through a corner window on the second floor, burning everything inside. A yellow flame erupted from the window. It was a signal and the attackers opened fire on the village ... "

Markar Melkonyan dedicated his work to the participation of his brother,²³ Monte Melkonian, one of the leaders of the international Armenian terrorist organization ASALA, in the occupation of Azerbaijani lands.

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https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qarada%C4%9Fli%C4%B1_q%C9%99tiam%C4%B1

²² Melkonian, Markar. My Brother's Road: An American's Fateful Journey to Armenia IB Tauris. 2005, 344 p.

²³ Talibli SA - ASALA 's participation in anti-Azerbaijani actions may create a new wave of terror - COMMENT

<https://az.trend.az/azerbaijan/politics/3274579.html>

ASALA (Hayastani Azatagrut'yan Hay Gaghtmi Banak) is an Armenian terrorist organization operating in 1975-1991.

It is recognized as a terrorist organization by the Republic of Turkey. The abbreviation of the name of this organization,

called "Secret Armenian Army for the Freedom of

Armenia", is "Armenian S ecret A rmy for the L iberation of A rmenia " in English . The main goal of ASALA is to es-

tablish a "Greater Armenia" state in an area that includes

Eastern Turkey, Northern Iran and the Nakhchivan and

Nagorno-Karabakh regions of Azerbaijan. ASALA mainly

carries out terrorist acts against Turkish and Azerbaijani citi-

zens. Its leader Akop Hakobyan played a major role in estab-

lishing relations with terrorist groups such as Abu Nidal and

Black September

¹⁸30 years have passed since the Garadagli tragedy

https://azertag.az/xeber/Qaradagli_faciesinden_30_il_otur-2017367

¹⁹ Pagayeva Q., Aslanov Sh. Garadagli Genocide: In the language of witnesses. (Dedicated to the memory of the victims of the genocide committed by the Armenian Armed Forces in Garadagli village of Khojavend region of Azerbaijan). Baku, "Science and education", 2013, p.105

²⁰ Pagayeva Q., Aslanov Sh. Garadagli Genocide: In the language of witnesses. (Dedicated to the memory of the victims of the genocide committed by the Armenian Armed Forces in Garadagli village of Khojavend region of Azerbaijan). Baku, "Science and education", 2013, S. 109

In 1989, Monte Melkonyan was invited to Armenia, where he was one of the active participants in the campaign of aggression against Azerbaijan. He was one of the direct leaders of genocide against civilians in Garadaghli, Khojaly and a number of other settlements in Azerbaijan. Markar Melkonyan writes in his book "My Brother's Way" about Monte's participation in the occupation of Garadaghli: It burned everything inside. A yellow flame erupted from the window. It was a signal and the attackers shot at the village. 48 Azerbaijanis were killed and taken prisoner on their way to a truck. The captives were taken to Stepanakert (Khankendi) and held there until they were exchanged for Armenian prisoners of war held by Azerbaijanis. gangs - ed.) threw 38 captives into a ditch on the outskirts of the village, including civilians, including women lar. The soldiers of the Arabo and Aramo detachments began to shoot the captives and cut them all with their knives, without exception. Edo, one of the five members of the patriotic group from Ashtarak, poured gasoline on several people and threw a burning match on them. As Monte approached the ditch, there were the remains of burnt corpses. ... In total, 53 Azerbaijanis were killed in and around Garadaghli in two days ...²⁴

Legal steps of the Republic of Azerbaijan with Garadaghli tragedy

In connection with the Garadaghli tragedy, the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Azerbaijan states that in order to destroy the Azerbaijanis as a national group, members of the Armenian armed forces on February 14-17, 1992 killed 9 minors, 10 women and 14 residents of Garadaghli village of Khojavend. Sixty-seven people were killed, including more than 60 men, 34 of them men. Two people were seriously injured and 9 were taken hostage. At the same time, they looted and burned residential buildings and government facilities. An investigation group has been set up to investigate crimes against peace and humanity, as well as war and other crimes committed by the separatist regime's armed forces and the Armenian Armed Forces against the local Azerbaijani population. At present, the Republican Military Prosecutor's Office is investigating under the relevant articles of the Criminal Code.²⁵

The report on the Garadaghli genocide episode of the criminal case No. 80377 investigated by the joint investigation-operational group of the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Azerbaijan states that "on the night of February 15-16, 1992, the Armenian armed gangs On February 29, 1992, the Karabakh inter-district prosecutor's office charged

Garadagli village residents of the former Martuni region with killing a resident of the village Hasanov Altay Mahammad oglu and Husenyov Khayal Habib oglu with a firearm . Criminal case No. 64526 was initiated and investigated under items 6 (old version). A number of investigative measures were taken, victims and witnesses were interrogated, forensic, forensic and forensic biological examinations were carried out, but the perpetrators were not identified. The last criminal case was held on 20 December 1992. was suspended in accordance with paragraph 3 of Article 209 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The above-mentioned criminal case was studied by the joint investigative task force established by the order of the Prosecutor General, the Minister of Internal Affairs and the Minister of National Security of the Republic of Azerbaijan on 18 December 2003, and on 20 December 1992 The decision was annulled and the criminal case was reopened and merged with criminal case number 80377, which is being processed by the joint investigation operation group.

The fact of intentional killing of 49 people and torture of 57 people as a result of an armed attack on Garadagli village by Armenian armed forces on February 15-17, 1992 On July 17, 2005 Deputy Prosecutor General of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Military Prosecutor of the Republic of Azerbaijan Lieutenant General of Justice Khanlar Valiyev was charged under Article 103 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan and the criminal case was investigated.

Illegal armed groups living in the Nagorno-Karabakh region of the Republic of Azerbaijan and exemplified by nationalist Armenians from the Republic of Armenia Marti-rosyan Vladimir Georgievich and Danielyan Slavik Makarovich, accused of forcible expulsion of Azerbaijanis legally located in the Khojavend (formerly Martuni) region without the grounds established by the norms and laws of the Republic of Azerbaijan, on June 2, 2008, and Nasibyan Grigory Yegiashovich on June 13, 2008. In 2008, a decision was made to prosecute him under Articles 103 and 107 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan. opened and searches were provided. "

²⁴ Pagayeva Q., Aslanov Sh. Garadaghli Genocide: In the language of witnesses. (Dedicated to the memory of the victims of the genocide committed by the Armenian Armed Forces in Garadagli village of Khojavend region of Azerbaijan). Baku, "Science and education", 2013, p. 99-101

²⁵ <https://read.az/society/574304>

The Case No. 80377 investigated by the Joint Investigation and Operational Group of the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the episode of the Garadaghli genocide states that "despite the fact that , that these criminal acts relate to crimes

against peace and humanity under Chapter 16 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan, which came into force on 1 September 2000, and that the United Nations General Assembly Article 75.5 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the non-application of the Convention adopted by the resolution of November 26, 1968 and entered into force on November 11, 1970, regardless of the time of the commission of the above-mentioned crimes . except for the provisions of this article limiting the period of bringing to justice the perpetrators of crimes against peace and humanity, as well as normative legal acts included in the legislative system of the Azerbaijan Republic in accordance with Article 151 of the Constitution of the Azerbaijan Republic (Constitution of the Azerbaijan Republic and acts adopted by referendum) If there is a conflict between the interstate agreements to which the Republic of Azerbaijan is a party, these international agreements shall be applied, and citizens of the Republic of Azerbaijan, foreigners or stateless persons who have committed such crimes shall be prosecuted and punished regardless of the place of crime. Article 2.3 of the CPC also defines other rules other than this Code in international agreements to which the Republic of Azerbaijan is a party. Article 7, paragraph 2, of the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, to which the Republic of Azerbaijan acceded on 25 December 2001 and adopted by the Council of Europe on 04.11.1950, provides for the application of the provisions of international treaties. not to prevent the prosecution or punishment of any person for any act or omission criminalized in accordance with the basic principles of law recognized by civilized countries at the time of its commission; If deprivation of life under Article 6 (3) of the International Covenant on Human Rights constitutes a crime of genocide, it must be borne in mind that no provision of this article is currently applicable to States Parties to the present Covenant on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide. not to give any person the right to withdraw from any obligation, no provision of this Article under paragraph 2 of Article 15 of the Covenant, any act or error which is a criminal offense in accordance with the principles of general law accepted by international law at the time of its commission. Martirosyan Vladimir Georgievich, Martirosyan Kamo Georgievich, Babayan Vartan Emilovich, Hayrapetyan Jasha Mukhanovich, Danielyan Slavik Arsenovich Convention on Punishment for Punishment for December 9, 1948 and Article 107 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan, as well as deportation crimes provided for in Article 107 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan Decisions were made to prosecute them under Articles 103 and 107 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the courts imposed a measure of restraint on them and the documents were sent to the relevant authorities for their search.²⁶

²⁶ Pagayeva Q., Aslanov Sh. Garadaghli Genocide: In the language of witnesses. (Dedicated to the memory of the

The Commissioner for Human Rights (Ombudsman) of the Republic of Azerbaijan Sabina Aliyeva called on the international community on the 30th anniversary of the Garadaghli tragedy. committed genocide. As a result of this bloody crime, Garadagli village was occupied and burned, 118 civilians were taken hostage and 68 of them were brutally killed. The continuation of the policy of aggression and ethnic cleansing pursued by the Armenian military-political leadership against Azerbaijanis, the Garadaghli genocide, which is an expression of hatred for the Azerbaijani people, must be legally assessed by international organizations, and the perpetrators of this crime against peace and humanity must be prosecuted.²⁷

The position of international and regional organizations on the Garadaghli tragedy

Azerbaijan has repeatedly sent letters to the UN , various international and regional organizations **regarding the Garadaghli tragedy** . The Red Cross condemned the killing of Azerbaijani civilians.

The result

In the early twentieth century, with the support of Armenians and regional and international forces, Azerbaijanis pursued a policy of racial and religious discrimination against the Azerbaijani people, occupied our lands, displaced the Azerbaijani people from historical Azerbaijani lands, and pursued a policy of ethnic cleansing and genocide against Turkic-Muslim peoples. Communicating the Garadaghli tragedy, one of such genocide, to both the local community and the world community is important in terms of studying the realities of Azerbaijan, the tragedies that befell the Azerbaijani people, the aggression, terror and occupation of the Azerbaijani people and state.

As a sign of deep respect for the memory of our martyrs who sacrificed their lives for the protection and territorial integrity of our historical and ancient lands, the Khojavend District Executive Power organized the Martyrs' Alley memorial complex in Yeni Khojavend settlement. At the same time, the "Martyrs" memorial complex was erected in memory of the martyrs and victims of the tragedy in "Yeni Garadagli" settlement at the expense of the residents of Garadagli village in 2012 at the expense of the residents of Garadagli village. Extensive commemoration ceremonies are being held in front of the monument in February with

victims of the genocide committed by the Armenian Armed Forces in Garadagli village of Khojavend region of Azerbaijan). Baku, "Science and education", 2013, p. 142-152.

²⁷ Ombudsman calls for Garadaghli tragedy

<https://apa.az/en/social/ombudsman-qaradagli-faciesi-ile-bagli-cagiris-edib-687236>

the participation of martyrs' families, the district community, members of the media and other guests. On the night of February 25-26, 2017, a "Memory" park was established in Khojavend settlement in memory of our brave soldiers who were heroically killed while preventing the provocation of the Armenian armed forces in the direction of Khojavend.

Note that, There are facts and information in the press, books and research conducted by Azerbaijani law enforcement agencies that 195 Armenians committed genocide, terrorism, deportation and other especially serious crimes against Azerbaijani citizens in Nagorno-Karabakh in 1988-1992. .

In my opinion, both the local and world community should know the historical circumstances of the genocide of Azerbaijanis, the causes, nature and consequences of the genocide against the Turkish-Muslim population, the historical goals of the Armenian-Dashnak, Bolshevik and foreign forces; To explain to the international community the goals of

regional and international forces supporting the implementation of the ugly intentions of the Armenian aggressors, the essence and significance of the measures taken by the Independent Republic of Azerbaijan in connection with the genocide of Azerbaijanis; to substantiate the genocide of Azerbaijanis as a crime against humanity based on historiography, archival materials, scientific literature, periodicals, photos, materials of the Extraordinary Commission of Inquiry of the Azerbaijan People's Republic (1918-1920), as well as historical documents, Baku, Guba, Shamakhi, Eastern Anatolia, The detailed historical facts about the genocide in the cities, settlements, villages and other regions of Nakhchivan, Zangazur, Salyan, Neftchala, Lankaran, Yerevan, Khoj, Salmas, Urmia regions of South Azerbaijan raja is important and significant. During the occupation of the villages of Jamilli, Karkijahan, Gushchular, Malibeyli, Meshali, Garadagli by the Armenian aggressors in November 1991-February 1992, the Armenian armed groups committed war crimes against the civilian population, the Khojaly tragedy, the Aghdaban tragedy, the Balligaya tragedy, as well as the Garadagli Information about the tragedy should be provided to international and regional organizations, the world press and research centers on the basis of detailed, factual, evidence and documents.

References

- Aliyoglu, S. (1993)Khojaly: [366 days have passed since the massacre committed by the "366th" division]. 525th Gazette. 26 February. p. 4.
- Encyclopedic dictionary of toponyms of Azerbaijan.* (2007) In II Volumes, 2nd Volume, Baku. "East-West", p. 24.
- Garadaghly Massacre through the eyes of witness.*<https://en.azvision.az/news/81073/garadaghly-massacre-through-the-eyes-of-witness.html>
- Georgios Maris, Floros Flouros & Ioannis Galariotis (2022) The Changing Security Landscape in South-Eastern Mediterranean: Assessing Turkey's Strategies as a Rising Power, *Journal of Balkan and Near Eastern Studies*, DOI: 10.1080/19448953.2022.2037962
- Gerard Toal & John O'Loughlin (2013) Land for Peace in Nagorny Karabakh? Political Geographies and Public Attitudes Inside a Contested De Facto State, *Territory, Politics, Governance*, 1:2, 158-182, DOI: 10.1080/21622671.2013.842184
- Hamza Karčić (2016) Khojaly: The Worst Massacre in the Nagorno-Karabakh War and Azerbaijan's Quest to Commemorate the Tragedy, *Journal of Muslim Minority Affairs*, 36:4, 597-601, DOI: 10.1080/13602004.2016.1257684

- Laurence Broers (2015) From "frozen conflict" to enduring rivalry: reassessing the Nagorny Karabakh conflict, *Nationalities Papers*, 43:4, 556-576, DOI: 10.1080/00905992.2015.1042852
- Litovkin, B. (1992) The paratroopers will cover the 366th regiment from Stepanakert. *Izvestia*. March 3
- Mammadov, E. (2008) Khojaly was under siege for four months: an operational plan was prepared at the headquarters of the 366th Motorized Rifle Regiment. *Two shores*. February 26.- p.5.
- Pagayeva Q. (2013) Aslanov Sh. Garadaghli Genocide: In the language of witnesses. (Dedicated to the memory of the victims of the genocide committed by the Armenian Armed Forces in Garadagli village of Khojavend region of Azerbaijan). Baku, *Science and education*, p. 31-33
- Rauf Garagozov (2013) Implicit measures of attitude change via narrative intervention in the Karabakh conflict, *Dynamics of Asymmetric Conflict*, 6:1-3, 98-109, DOI: 10.1080/17467586.2013.861919
- Salaev, Q. (1992) 40 days Khojaly: "Heroes" 366th regiment is dedicated. *Youth of Azerbaijan*. April 4. p. 2
- Sebastian Muth (2014) War, language removal and self-identification in the linguistic landscapes of Nagorno-Karabakh, *Nationalities Papers*, 42:1, 63-87, DOI: 10.1080/00905992.2013.856394
- Today, Azerbaijan commemorates the 26th anniversary of the Garadaghly massacre committed by Armenian armed forces. <http://defence.az/en/news/124474/26-years-pass-since-garadaghly-massacre>
- Valiyev, X. (2011) The participation of servicemen and other persons of the 366th Regiment in the Khojaly genocide has been fully proved. *New Azerbaijan*. February 26. p.11.
- Vincenc Kopecek, Tomas Hoch & Vladimir Baar (2016) Conflict Transformation and Civil Society: The Case of Nagorno-Karabakh, *Europe-Asia Studies*, 68:3, 441-459, DOI: 10.1080/09668136.2016.1147528
- Zulfugarli M.P. (1992) Garadagli tragedy: Armenian terror in Nagorno-Karabakh: February 17, Baku, *Law*, p.10

Internet resources

- Subhan Talibli - What are the main and factual land claims of Armenians over Karabakh? COMMENT
<https://sia.az/en/news/social/771630.html>
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qarada%C4%9Fl%C4%B1_q%C9%99tl%C4%B1
- <http://www.xocavend-ih.gov.az/news/1056.html>
- https://azertag.az/xeber/Qaradagli_faciesi_qurbanlarinin_xatiresi_anilib-1247282
- 2nd Khojaly genocide - 19th anniversary of Garadaghli tragedy completed-- <http://www.yalquzaq.com/?p=18069>
- 30 years have passed since the Garadagli tragedy - https://azertag.az/xeber/Qaradagli_faciesinden_30_il_otur-2017367
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qarada%C4%9Fl%C4%B1_q%C9%99tl%C4%B1
- Melkonian, Markar (2005) *My Brother's Road: An American's Fateful Journey to Armenia* IB Tauris. 344 p.

Talibli S.A. - ASALA 's participation in anti-Azerbaijani actions may create a new wave of terror - COMMENT

<https://az.trend.az/azerbaijan/politics/3274579.html>

<https://oxu.az/society/574304>

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